

Biotechnology for Animal Ecology

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Introduction

The world has ever been struggling to conserve nature and natural resources. The simultaneous increase of food demand with the increase in human population has hammered our 'nature conservation' concepts. We are threateningly losing our animal genetic resources. Westernized notions of what constitutes a 'good breed' have spoilt our concepts of native breeds. The past 3 decades have seen the extensive use of 'elite' germplasm being used for crossing with indigenous breeds, leading to large-scale propagation of exotic breeds at the cost of native breeds, some of which are now truly endangered. Native breeds are known for their disease and climate resistant characters, they have unique genetic traits which have unfortunately not been well understood. The food crisis has also led to the extension of agricultural lands by means of extensive deforestation, taking over the natural habitats of wildlife species. Natural calamities and anthropogenic activities like poaching and invading forest areas for building shelters have also reduced biodiversity counts. We need better conservation strategies, digging into molecular levels in order to both conserve and preserve our slowly vanishing Animal Genetic Resources (Animal Genetic Resources). Advanced biotechnological strategies are now playing a vital role in safeguarding them.

Figure 1. Using genetic resources for strengthening animal ecology

Source: Degnarain and Phelan (2018). 5 Biotechnologies that might help save endangered species. Fortune.

Numerous conservation strategies are in practice and have shown promising results. However, newer strategies are also in the pipeline taking into consideration the still depleting AGR and their importance in human survival. Biotechnological intervention in conservation strategies has made a humongous contribution to the preservation as well as modification of our AGR. Following are major biotechnological conservation strategies:

1. **Genetic resource banking (GRB):** Ex-situ cryopreservation of germplasm, specifically spermatozoa, oocytes or embryos, and other cells/tissues or DNA from endangered species is used worldwide for its practical viability. Frozen semen straws are widely used in different farms which facilitates insemination of females with higher quality semen without the male being practically present. This safeguards the existence of an entire species without the males being unnecessarily kept in captivity. Collection of oocytes for preservation brings along the constrain of well understanding the estrous cycle and ovulation time of the particular species which is more difficult in case of feral animals. Embryo cryopreservation presents the advantage of storing the entire genome of a species and allows the enormous potential for protecting and managing species, population integrity and heterozygosity. Auto-grafting and xeno-grafting of ovaries and testes also have potential in future cloning-based conservation programs.
2. **Assisted reproductive Technologies (ART):** Reproductive fitness gets impaired when animals are kept in captivity due to unavailability of natural habitat, non-adapted diet and other

managerial loopholes for which conservation breeding can be optimized with Assisted Reproductive Techniques. Artificial Insemination is the most commonly used ART with high success rates recorded in farm animals. Spotty, the spotted deer in Nehru Zoological Park, Hyderabad was the 1st wild animal to be successfully inseminated in India in March 2006, puffing us with hopes of promising wildlife conservation through AI. Embryo Transplantation (ET) and In-Vitro Fertilization (IVF) are also thoroughly used in veterinary researches, with appreciable success rates. However, these strategies in wildlife are far from being routinely used and still have a really poor success rate due to scanty knowledge on wildlife reproductive physiology and anatomy. Laparoscopic Ovum Pick Up (LPOU) along with IVF is a golden combination used in the conservation of Jaguar, Puma and buffalos in foreign countries. Micromanipulation techniques such as Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI) are gaining popularity as a conservation strategy in male infertility cases. Success rates are promising in equine conservation. This brings rays of hope in safeguarding the depleting feral horse population in Dibru Saikhowa National Park in Assam.

3. ***Cloning***: In 1996 Scottish researchers attempted to clone a female Finn-Dorset sheep. 300 empty enucleated eggs were injected with the nucleus of the Finn-Dorset sheep. Only 30 embryos were created out of the 300 eggs. Out of the 30 embryos implanted in surrogate mothers, only 5 lambs took birth. Only 1 out of the 5 lambs could survive till adulthood. She was named Dolly. Since 1996 even though technologies got advanced, creating clones still is a tedious process. Successful cloning requires three components: DNA from the animal to be cloned, a recipient egg to receive that DNA and a female to gestate the resulting embryo. The resulting offspring has the same genetic complement as the original donor, except for the mitochondrial DNA, which is derived from the recipient. This technique is called Somatic Cell Nuclear Transfer (SCNT). Both recipient egg and recipient female selection become crucial for the survivability of the embryo. Both should be closely related to the species of the animal to be cloned. Cloning is more vital for species that are on the verge of extinction.

4. ***Sexed Semen***: Semen bearing either X or Y chromosome to produce progenies of desired sex is called sexed semen. Sexed semen is majorly used in dairy farms to obtain female calves for increasing profit making. However, it is also emerging as an AGR conservation strategy. There are many wildlife species that naturally live in female dominated groups. The sex ratio of such

species becomes crucial for their survival. Also, excessive male births may lead to male to male aggression in the wild. Sexed semen helps maintain male to female ratio, being biased towards any sex considering the need. A major challenge in using sexed semen in wildlife will be the tendency of males to produce pleiomorphic spermatozoa.

5. **Stem cell technology:** Pluripotent stem cells derived from the early embryonic stage have the ability to differentiate into any tissue of the body except for extra-embryonic tissues like the placenta. Stem cell technology is now extensively used in medical science for different lines of treatment. It also stands out as an effective conservation strategy for endangered animal species. Scientists have also found out ways of reverting specialized cells of the body to an embryo-like stage. These cells are termed induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs). So basically, even a skin cell can rebuild the entire lost species once again. Scientists are still working on how to effectively convert stem cells to embryos or coax them to produce matured sperms and ovum for IVF. This study is presently done on mice and when perfected will be used in the conservation of the Northern White Rhinos of which we are left with only 2 females on the planet. Apart from domestic and wild animal conservation, iPSCs are utilized in developing laboratory-grown animal products which shall lessen the discrimination of animals for meat, leather and fur.

6. **Genomics:** Genomics is the study of the entire DNA of a species. The Human Genomic Project took 20 years to complete. However, with the advancement of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), it has been reduced to 15 mins for sequencing the DNA of any species. Study of the entire DNA gives immense information about the entire physiology and genetic makeup of the animal. It gives information about the effective population size, demographic history, population structure, evolution of the species over time and most important presence and extent of inbreeding in a population. Comparative genome studies of different animal species let us know of how closely they are related. These at times reveal shocking genetic similarities between two phenotypically dissimilar species. This helps in choosing which species to be conserved. All these bioinformatic data provide genomic insights to improve the monitoring, management, and restoration of endangered wildlife. Genomic insight is now the foundation for diverse applications of biotechnology.

Conclusion

The world is in grave need to preserve and conserve its ecology. Animals, as we all know, play a vital role in maintaining ecological balance. Extinction of even a single species can disrupt this balance in terms that are out of our understanding. Sadly, we are losing new species every year. However, biotechnology now has built inside us strong hopes of species preservation and conservation. It has the potential to not only conserve endangered species but also to reanimate already extinct animals. Sudan, the last male White Rhinoceros of Africa died on the 19th of March, 2018 but his cells are still alive in the labs of San Diego Zoo Institute for Conservation in the form of pluripotent stem cells.

Figure 2. Sudan, the last male Northern White Rhinoceros, Africa
Source: Ami Vitale, National Geographic Magazine, 2019

However, deriving positive results with the application of biotechnology requires taking into consideration the reproductive physiology, anatomy of the reproductive tract, availability of cells for preservation, suitable donor and recipient of gametes, mothering ability of surrogates, neonatal care and cost effectiveness of the technologies. Only such holistic considerations shall provide fruitful results. Restoration of animal ecology through biotechnology might be slow paced but our hopes are high.